

Use of microcredit for household income and consumption smoothing by low income communities

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Abstract

This paper discusses findings of a study that investigated income, savings and consumption patterns of low income people, and critical factors that influence the use of microcredit- a form of small instant loans targeted for low income people- for household income and consumption smoothing. The sample of the study consisted of households from low income communities living in a lower-middle income country- Sri Lanka. It was found that microcredit borrowers were using the loans for purposes that can be identified as income and consumption smoothing, which is beyond the ideas and intended practice of microcredit. The findings suggests that the consequences of using microcredit for income and consumption smoothing could be costly for households and the society at large.

Key words: borrowing, consumption smoothing, credit, debt, income smoothing, small instant loans, loans, microcredit.

Introduction

The use of various forms of instant credit has been observed worldwide. Credit cards are used as a tool to bolster purchasing power or a source of revolving credit (Wickramasinghe & Gurugamage, 2012). Auto titles, payday loans, advance tax refunds as well as tangible assets in pawning are used as collateral to advance credit, which should be repaid in a short period of time (Francis, 2010; Urahn, 2012). Previous research showed that consumers unequivocally appreciate the convenience of small instant loans. They use the credit to pay for basic necessities; planned purchases like houses and cars that some would otherwise be unable to afford as well as to cover unexpected expenses and misaligned cash flow (Autio et al, 2009; Erasmus & Mathunjwa, 2011; Jahiruddin et al, 2011; Patel et al., 2012). The consumers who use credit to balance out a misaligned cash flow are more likely to be repeat borrowers (Bianchi & Levy, 2013; Jahiruddin et al., 2011).

In the present study, we investigated a form of instant loans – microcredit - targeted especially for low income people. Unlike above mentioned different forms of small instant loans,

which can be obtained without a specific planned purpose (Autio et al, 2009), microcredit institutions deliver microcredit for an intended purpose, i.e., invest in income generating activities. As introduced by Dr. Muhammad Yunus, a recipient of the Nobel Peace Prize 2006 for founding the Grameen Bank and pioneering the concepts of microcredit and microfinance, the main objective of microcredit is to facilitate people in low income communities commencing income generating self-employment projects known as micro-entrepreneurship (Yunus, 2004). However, evidence suggests that low income people use microcredit for income and consumption smoothing instead of income generating self-employment projects (Bylander, 2015; Hung, 2003; Karim, 2008; Nkamnebe & Idemobi, 2011; Zeller, 1999).

The terms *income smoothing* and *consumption smoothing* are widely used in the economics literature when describing household risk due to income shortages (Busato et al., 2008; Gerry & Li, 2010; Gervais & Klein, 2010; Morduch, 1995; Ravallion & Chaudhuri, 1997; Takasaki et al., 2010; Townsend, 1995). When households experience temporary losses of income, they face with idiosyncratic earning shock or risk that is peculiar to the individual or household. An important aspect of household risk-sharing is the extent to which household consumption respond to idiosyncratic earning shocks (Gervais & Klein, 2010). Coping with risk can occur at two stages, which function as substitutes for each other, i.e., income smoothing and consumption smoothing (Morduch, 1995; Seefeldt, 2015). Households can protect themselves from adverse income shocks before they occur by income smoothing actions such as making conservative production or employment choices and diversifying economic activities (Morduch, 1995). Households can take consumption smoothing actions to help insulate consumption patterns from income variability after shocks occur by borrowing and saving, depleting and accumulating non-financial assets, adjusting labor supply, and entering into formal and informal insurance arrangements (Morduch, 1995; Seefeldt, 2015). Hence, income and consumption smoothing refer to various ways in which households attempt to replace short-term losses of household income.

In this context, by taking a sample from economically disadvantaged communities living in Sri Lanka, we investigated situations where low income households divert microcredit loans for income and consumption smoothing to maintain their living standards and its consequences. The specific objectives of the study were 1) to investigate income, savings and consumption

patterns of low income people, and 2) to identify critical factors that influence the use of microcredit for household income and consumption smoothing.

Review of literature

Disposable income and risk-coping via income and consumption smoothing

Disposable income or income available for consumption and income generation can be identified as an important aspect in evaluating actions and behaviour of consumers (Gervais & Klein, 2010; Morduch, 1995; Seefeldt, 2015; Zeller, 1999). Falling below the required level of income depicts a risk faced by a household. In such circumstances, a household can engage in ex-ante and ex-post actions to generate disposable income (Busato et al., 2008; Morduch, 1995; Seefeldt, 2015; Takasaki et al., 2010; Wik, 1999; Zeller, 1999). Ex-ante income is the income a household anticipates earning through the use of its physical, human and social capital. If ex-ante income is lower than the minimum level of income required to satisfy the need for food and other basic necessities, a household engages in ex-post activities to generate additional income to decrease the variance in income and consumption.

In detail, on the one hand, access to savings, credit and insurance increase the expected value or reduce the variance of ex-ante income. Savings accumulated in prior periods can be divested and used for the acquisition of physical, human and social capital needed for income generation. Credit can also increase the capital base of a household. A household can also enter into insurance contracts (or of insurance substitutes) for self-protection to safeguard itself against risks (Notten & de Crombrughe, 2012; Morduch, 1995; Seefeldt, 2015; Zeller, 1999). Accordingly, the feeding of savings, credit and insurance into ex-ante income make a household more resilient to income shocks. Therefore, risk-coping via income smoothing includes all possible ex-ante actions by a household to smooth out income and thereby smooth adverse income shocks before these occur in current and future periods (Busato et al., 2008; Takasaki et al., 2010; Zeller, 1999). On the other hand, access to savings, credit and insurance can influence ex-post income. A household could demand credit for consumption or production credit could be diverted to consumption; assets could be sold (i.e. liquidation of previous savings); and/or insurance claims could be voiced through informal social networks, social security schemes or crop/livestock insurance schemes (Morduch, 1995; Notten & de Crombrughe, 2012; Skoufias, 2003; Zeller, 1999). Accordingly, the feeding of savings, credit and insurance into ex-post

income make a household more resilient against income shocks. Therefore, risk-coping via consumption smoothing includes all possible ex-post actions by the household to smooth out disposable income and thereby smooth consumption patterns from income variability in current and in future periods (Busato et al., 2008; Gerry & Li, 2010; Krueger & Perri, 2005; Skoufias, 2003). When considering household actions of income and consumption smoothing, “one cannot simply look at the smoothness of consumption and know which type of smoothing mechanism is at work. Indeed, the two types can act as substitutes for each other (Morduch, 1995). “If insurance or credit is available, the need for income smoothing is less urgent; if non-expensive means of income smoothing exist, consumption-smoothing becomes less important” (Morduch, 1995, p. 104). Gervais and Klein (2010) found that households with considerable financial assets do not smooth consumption compared to households with less financial assets; households with relatively high income do not smooth consumption compared to households with relatively low income.

Overall, households can use a number of coping strategies to smooth out income shortages. First, households may maintain their consumption levels by depleting savings, selling assets or durable goods or borrowing money. These strategies are identified in the economics literature as self-insurance (Notten & de Crombrughe, 2012). Second, households can request and obtain financial support from institutions like banks and social networks like family and friends through formal or informal transfer arrangements and insurance policies (Notten & de Crombrughe, 2012; Takasaki et al., 2010). These strategies are identified in the economics literature as risk-sharing among members of society (Notten and de Crombrughe, 2012). Third, households can take effort to maintain income rather than consumption *per se* by cultivating any available land, producing basic goods and services, adjusting their labour supply or delivering productivity efforts (Morduch, 1995; Notten & de Crombrughe, 2012; Wik, 1999). Therefore, the availability of capital in the form of physical, human and social and access to financial products in the form of savings, credit and insurance increase the risk-coping capacity of households via income and consumption smoothing in situations where disposable income is falling below the required levels for basic household requirements (Gerry & Li, 2010; Takasaki et al., 2010; Wik, 1999). In this paper we are confined to investigate low income households’ risk-coping via debt – microcredit.

Poverty, low income communities and microcredit

The term poverty describes an inability to attain a minimum standard of living (United Nations, 2009). Almost half of the world's population live on less than 1.50 US Dollars a day, which represents an absolute and internationally comparable income-focused threshold to poverty (United Nations, 2009). Koku (2011, p. 271) states "paradoxically, as the so-called middle-class shrinks the percentage of people living in poverty around the world increases". One of the main causes of poverty is weak or lack of attachment to the labour market (Kozak et al., 2012; Millennium Development Goal [MDG] Task Force, 2010). The world's low income people have limited opportunities for decent employment, they experience higher rates of involuntary unemployment, and mainly engage in vulnerable employment that includes own-account workers and contributing family workers (International Labour Organisation [ILO], 2002; Kozak et al., 2012). The lack of access to decent employment not only deprives them from regular income but also deprives them from unemployment benefit, pension and health insurance, and they are less connected to the formal financial system (Yunus, 2004). As a result, they have limited disposable income, and face idiosyncratic risk of failing to attain minimum levels of income required to lead a valuable and valued life (Seefeldt, 2015; Skoufias, 2003; Wik, 1999; Zeller, 1999).

In these circumstances, to decrease variances of income and consumption, people seek credit (borrowing or loan) to increase their risk-coping/bearing capacity to smooth out household income and consumption patterns. When a household requests credit for risk-coping from an institution operating in a formal financial system, the availability of capital in the form of physical, human and social as security for credit as well as credit history will determine the repayment capacity, and therefore the creditworthiness. For instance, physical capital such as a land title or social capital as a guarantor can serve as loan collateral (Chowdhury et al., 2005; Schroeder, 2010). However, access to means to risk-coping "varies considerably between relatively rich and poor households, where rich households have a much better access to these means than poorer households" (Wik, 1999, p. 330). Low income households' entitlement to land title and other inheritance is rare (Unterhalter, 2009). Due to lower levels of education, human capital is limited (Kozak et al., 2012). As a result, low income people are less connected to formal financial products of savings, credit and insurance as they are not creditworthy (Renwick, 2011; Yunus, 2004).

It is well documented that improved access to affordable credit for low income people is a vehicle for breaking the vicious circle of economic, social and demographic entrapment experienced (Karim, 2008; Yunus, 2004). Microcredit institutions are established to deliver credit for low income people in the form of capital for income generating activities using their entrepreneurial abilities (Grameen Foundation, 2014; Hung, 2003). These institutions deliver credit taking the mutual trust (social capital) of a collection of low income people as collateral (group-based collateral), identified as thrift groups or self-help groups (Edward & Olsen, 2006; Ghalib et al., 2015; Grameen Foundation, 2014; Hung, 2003; Kozak et al., 2012; Norwood, 2011; MDG Task Force, 2010; Sarkar & Singh, 2006; Schroeder, 2010). Self-help groups are formed as a collection of 10 to 15 individuals (each representing his/her household), who come from the same socio-economic background; unequal power and diversity can derail the ideas of solidarity and shared interest in self-help groups. A member of each self-help group accepts liability for the repayment of his/her microcredit loan and joint liability for the repayment of each other's loan (Hung, 2003; Karim, 2008; Omorodion, 2007; Sarkar & Singh, 2006). If a member of the group defaults, the entire group becomes ineligible for further loans (Hung, 2003; Karim, 2008; Sarkar & Singh, 2006). This group liability based on mutual trust is the fundamental principle of microcredit for low income people, who do not have physical collateral or credit history. The literature identifies mutual trust as a must for survival in low income communities; the cost of losing trust in their communities is immeasurable (Mukherjee and Kundu, 2012; Norwood, 2011). Nonetheless, even at microcredit institutions borrowers' end-up paying hidden costs such as entrance fees, cancellation fees, late fees and mandatory savings in addition to interest, which suggest a higher cost for borrowing. Still, the interest rate is much lower than the rate charged by private money-lenders (Karim, 2008).

Main target group of microcredit - women

The concept of microcredit is gender bias, and identifies women as the main target group since they are known to be entrepreneurially motivated by the need for survival (Grameen Foundation, 2014; Yunus, 2004). Even in low income communities women are identified for their characteristic of being consistently better in promptness and reliability in repaying credit (Grameen Foundation, 2014; Yunus, 2004). Further, the identification of women living in low income communities as the main target group for the delivery of microcredit make them an equal

partner in the achievement of equitable development (Grameen Foundation, 2014; Ward and Mouly, 2013; Yunus, 2004). The previous studies by Ghalib et al. (2015), Ssendi and Anderson (2009), Unterhalter (2009), Omorodion (2007), Edward and Olsen (2006), and Albee and Reid (1992) empirically investigated these arguments in different country contexts. All these studies supported the fact that microcredit is delivered exclusively for women. According to Edward and Olsen (2006), two factors appear to underlie this gender bias. On the one hand, women are more responsible and aware than men about the household needs, and therefore, they are less likely to squander borrowings; they are less likely to default on repayment since they highly value their honour in the community. On the other hand, women living in low income communities are “doubly oppressed by virtue of both their poverty and their subordinate status to men in their households”, and as a result they see “collective success as a way to realize greater empowerment and emancipation of women from traditional social structures” (Edward and Olsen, 2006, p. 34). Mukherjee and Kundu (2012) and Hoque and Itohara (2009) also supported this argument.

However, several previous studies showed that microcredit schemes failed to empower women in different country contexts (Fernando, 1997; Goetz & Gupta, 1996; Izugbara, 2004; Kabeer, 2001; Murthy, 2012). For instance, Izugbara (2004) found that women’s access to borrowing does not enhance their ability to address social issues, which could give them a feeling of empowerment. Kabeer (2001), Fernando (1997) and Goetz and Gutpa (1996) also provided similar findings. Goetz and Gutpa (1996) argued that the delivery of microcredit for women weakened the social position of women. Some previous studies such as Ghalib et al. (2015), Saeed et al. (2013), Murthy (2012) Ssendi and Anderson (2009) and Hussain (2003) argued that women use microcredit loans for the general welfare of the household ensuring the objectives of microcredit. However, the use of microcredit for smoothing actions is beyond the ideas and intended practice of microcredit (Grameen Foundation, 2014; Yunus, 2004), as discussed in the next section.

Microcredit for smoothing income and consumption

The ultimate aim of microcredit is long-term capital mobilization by allowing low income people to participate in the formal financial system through savings-led microfinance – “to bank the unbankables”, as opposed to income and consumption smoothing (Grameen Foundation, 2014;

Karim, 2008; Sarkar & Singh, 2006; Yunus, 2004). However, microcredit is seen as an effective option for smoothing household income and consumption (Albee & Reid, 1992; Bylander, 2015; Ghalib et al., 2015; Jahiruddin et al., 2011; Murthy, 2012; Norwood, 2011; Unterhalter, 2009). For instance, Ghalib et al. (2015) provided evidence of spending microcredit loans on nutrition, clothing, improvements in dwelling characteristics, and as household income in Pakistan. Hussain (2003) found that microcredit borrowers spend more on monthly per capita expenditure, living conditions and children's schooling in Pakistan. Albee and Reid (1992) identified the use of microcredit for smoothing income and consumption in Sri Lanka while Schroeder (2010) provided evidence for the same in Bangladesh. Jahiruddin et al. (2011) showed that microcredit contributed to poverty among borrowers, who use the borrowing for emergency purposes and household expenditure in Bangladesh. Seefeldt (2015), Gervais and Klein (2010) and Hoque and Itohara (2009) found evidence that low income people were often forced to trade the long-term goal of improving their lives for short-term survival by spending the borrowing on school uniforms and other supplies for their children as well as goods required for their households.

When credit is used for entrepreneurial activities, the funds can be recycled and loaned-out repeatedly creating a self-sustainable process. However, when credit is used for smoothing income and consumption, negative consequences may emerge heightening the vulnerabilities of low income people. In a recent study conducted in Cambodia, Bylander (2015) provided evidence that low income groups with a lack of assets and opportunities struggle to repay their microcredit loans, forcing them to repay through waged labour both within and outside the country (Bylander, 2015). In a similar vein, Chowdhury et al. (2005) stated poor households simply become poorer through the additional burden of debt while Yartey and Birzescu (2015) stated that borrowers were subjected to various levels of surveillance as they struggle to pay back loans. On the contrary, Nkamnebe and Idemobi (2011) suggested that low income people obtain credit with the intention of non-payment, suggesting low income groups are irresponsible and unreliable borrowers (not creditworthy). Edward and Olsen (2006) found that microcredit borrowers in India felt that it is deceptive to identify their groups as self-help groups or thrift groups, and preferred to identify merely as "credit groups". In this regard, Karim (2008) argued that if the term credit is replaced with debt, debt-related dependencies, which are linked through the relations of debt that regulate present behaviour and future pay-offs, can be identified among economically disadvantaged communities.

The repeated use of credit and the use of credit for unproductive purposes such as to repay earlier credit and interest by low income households raised concerns over the real cost of small instant loans (Jahiruddin et al., 2011; Melzer, 2011; Seefeldt, 2015). Jahiruddin et al. (2011) found that the use of microcredit for unproductive purposes exacerbate poverty among rural low income communities in Bangladesh. The use of small instant loans cause low income communities to become poorer due to poor credit management. Seefeldt (2015, p. 264) states “if the debtor lacks the funds to repay the debt and is thus living beyond his or her means, having this kind of debt may signal irresponsible spending, a lack of self-control, or a low level of financial literacy”. People living in low income communities, with limited experience and lower education levels can be identified as vulnerable consumers, who could get trapped in a spiral of overspending, serious financial bondage and debt. People who borrow various forms of small instant loans, struggle deeper in “debt traps” than before, irrespective of their geographic location (country/region) (Autio et al., 2009; Erasmus & Mathunjwa, 2011; Francis, 2010; Melzer, 2011; Patel et al., 2012; Trumbull, 2012). Although the borrowing of small instant loans is potentially detrimental to the individual, household and the wider economy, the demand for small instant loans will continue for the foreseeable future. Microcredit institutions operating across the world have succeeded in instant cash transfers in the form of credit to low income people (Ghalib et al., 2015; Grameen Foundation, 2014; Hung, 2003). However, limited attention has been directed at understanding the use of microcredit for household income and consumption smoothing, in comparison to the popularity of its use among low income people around the world.

Based on the literature reviewed above such as Bylander (2015), Ghalib et al. (2015), Norwood (2011) and Zeller (1999) that suggested socio-demographic characteristics of the borrower and his/her household may influence the use of microcredit for income and consumption smoothing, it is hypothesized:

H1: Socio-demographic characteristics of low income people influence the use of microcredit for income and consumption smoothing.

Based on the literature reviewed above such as Bylander (2015), Kozak et al. (2012), Renwick (2011), MDG Task Force (2010), Skoufias (2003) and Zeller (1999) that suggested

income and borrowing history may influence the use of microcredit for income and consumption smoothing, it is hypothesized:

H2: Income and borrowing history of low income people influence the use of microcredit for income and consumption smoothing.

Based on the literature reviewed above such as Mukherjee and Kundu (2012), Norwood (2011), Renwick (2011), Karim (2008), Omorodion (2007), Sarkar and Singh (2006), Hung (2003) and Skoufias (2003) that suggested microcredit terms and conditions and distance to microfinance institution may influence the use of microcredit for income and consumption smoothing, it is hypothesized:

H3: Microcredit terms and conditions and distance to microfinance institution influence the use of microcredit for income and consumption smoothing.

Method

Population and sample

Sri Lanka is currently rated as a lower-middle income country with a population of around 20 million people. The country has achieved considerable progress in reducing poverty. In 2005, the percentage of people who live on less than 1.25 US Dollars a day measure was at 10.3% with a target of achieving 7.5% by the end of 2015 (United Nations, 2009, p. 27). However, development initiatives have not been equally distributed across 22 administrative districts of the country. As a result, isolated communities living in poverty can be identified.

The present study was conducted in an administrative district, which is ranked as one with the lowest average household income in the country as per the Household Income and Expenditure Survey 2009/10 of the Census and Statistics of Sri Lanka. We identified 145 active self-help groups formed by microfinance institutions with the help of the office of Divisional Secretariat. In identifying these groups, we excluded inactive groups with arrears in more than three (3) monthly instalments (including interest). We considered these 145 groups as the population of our study. Each self-help group had 10-12 members, representing his/her household. Considering time and cost constraints, 58 groups were randomly selected as the sample (40% of the population). All the groups were linked with a microfinance institution operating in the area. A microcredit delivery system via self-help groups does not allow several

members in a particular group to apply for a loan at one particular time. The system operates in such a way that if a member of the group defaults, the entire group becomes ineligible for further loans. To qualify for a loan, a member should be free from prior borrowing taken through the group (i.e., should have settled any previous loan successfully). Therefore, in selecting the respondents, we selected the member, who had the most recent borrowing in each group at the time of data collection in 2015. In selecting these respondents, we have not made any effort to pre-identify the purpose that microcredit loans were taken for, although we had a specific interest in income and consumption smoothing. At the end of the data collection, 53 complete responses were collected, yielding 91% response rate (53/58). Table 1 shows the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents.

Table 1

Measures

A structured face-to-face interview schedule was used to collect primary data from respondents concerning socio-demographic characteristics, income and savings patterns, prior borrowing, microcredit borrowing, and terms and conditions of microcredit borrowing. Accordingly, we used the data:

- to describe socio-demographic characteristics including the age of borrower, total number of members in the household, number of dependents, highest level of education of borrower, community type, and nature of residency in the area (refer to Table 1).
- to describe income and history of borrowing including income, income source, savings, and unpaid prior borrowing (refer to Table 3).
- to describe the amount of microcredit borrowing and purposes for which the borrowing was actually utilized (refer to Table 4 for purpose, and Table 5 for credit amount).
- to describe terms and conditions of microcredit borrowing including repayment period, annual interest rate, instalment amount, upfront fee and distance to microfinance institution (refer to Table 5)
- to confirm that our respondents came from economically disadvantaged communities. For this purpose, we used the Progress out of Poverty Index (PPI), a client poverty

measurement tool of Grameen Foundation designed in 2010 for Sri Lanka that measures 10 household characteristics which are strongly correlated with income and consumption (Schreiner, 2010). Table 2 shows the 10 characteristics (not the scoring) of PPI against sample respondents. Based on the answers to these 10 characteristics, a score was computed, which ranges from 0 (most likely below a poverty line) to 100 (least likely below a poverty line), and the scores themselves have only relative units (Progress out of Poverty, 2015). The average score for our sample respondents was 34 (for scoring refer to - Progress out of Poverty, 2015). This figure is interpreted (using the poverty score card) as 93.2% of respondents came from low income households. This confirmed that our respondents represented the category of low income people. This was the basis for us to proceed with the data analysis.

Table 2

Methods of data analysis

The variables of credit amount, repayment period, annual interest rate, instalment amount, upfront fee, monthly income, age of borrower, total number of members in the household, and number of dependents were assessed by the natural logarithmic transformation of actual amounts. The highest level of education of the borrower (0 = primary, 1 = secondary), community type (0 = village, 1 = estate), nature of residency in the area (0 = native, 1 = migrant), previous unpaid borrowing (0 = no, 1 = yes), income source (0 = daily wage, 1 = self-employment/monthly pay) and distance to microfinance institution (0 = less than 10 kilometers, 1 = more than 10 kilometers) were binary coded.

The 14 variables shown in Table 6 were screened for robustness using theory-driven numerical methods as well as theory-driven graphical methods (IBM-SPSS Statistics, 2012). The data screening suggested that the variables were normally distributed. We used Andrews' Wave as the robust estimate for the variables and observed that variables had estimates closer to their respective mean values. We used Shapiro-Wilk as a test of normality, and found that test values were closer to one (1) and not significant, suggesting variables fit the normal curve well. Finally, we created Q-Q plots for each variable to observe how well a theoretical distribution (i.e., the

normal distribution) models the empirical data, and the plots suggested that the variables are normally distributed along fitted lines. After yielding satisfactory results from this screening, we used correlation and regression analysis to test the hypotheses.

Findings and discussion

The first objective of the study inquired into income, savings and consumption patterns of low income people. As shown in Table 3, respondents were engaged as either day labourers or in self-employment/wage employment. The daily waged respondents neither had constant work throughout a particular month nor regular monthly income. Altogether, wage employment and day labourers could be identified as engaged in job categories that are not recognized, regulated or protected by existing legal or regulatory frameworks of ILO (2002). Respondents with income generating self-employment were in small-scale farming, domestic tailoring, brick making, pottery, mushroom cultivation, poultry and manufacturing coir products. These types of self-employment activities can be identified as non-remunerative work undertaken in income-producing enterprises (ILO, 2002). Many of these activities were affected by weather patterns, technology and natural disasters such as floods. All respondents had (100%) unpaid prior borrowing obtained by either securing land title/self-employment as a guarantee or pawning. The majority had borrowed from a financial institution or cooperative while a minority had borrowed from informal money-lenders.

Table 3

Table 4 shows purposes for which microcredit were actually utilized. It is evident from Table 4 that all microcredit borrowers were using the loans for purposes that can be identified as income and consumption smoothing actions as reviewed in the literature, instead of the intended purpose of micro-entrepreneurship.

Table 4

Table 5 shows terms and conditions of microcredit used for smoothing income and consumption. Microcredit borrowers repay on average 21% of average monthly income (4600/22000) as monthly instalment (without taking into account the interest rate). The average annual interest rate was 29%. Loans were taken with many hidden costs, such as registration fee, upfront fee, sanction for delay in instalment payment, and sanction on loan default. However, borrowers experienced short credit processing period with no individual produced collateral but based on group collateral.

Table 5

The second objective of the study inquired into critical factors that influenced the use of microcredit for household income and consumption smoothing. We used 15 variables described in *Measures* to identify the most important factors that influence the amount of credit asked for income and consumption smoothing. These 15 variables can be broadly categorized as follows:

- microcredit terms and conditions (i.e., repayment period, annual interest rate, instalment amount, upfront fee, and distance to microfinance institution),
- income and borrowing history (i.e., monthly income, income source, and the existence of unpaid prior borrowing), and
- socio- demographic characteristics of the borrower and his/her household (i.e., age of the borrower, total number of members in the household, number of dependents, highest level of education of the borrower, nature of residency in the area, and community type).

Of these variables, the existence of unpaid prior borrowing had been excluded from correlation and regression analysis since all respondents (100%) had unpaid prior borrowing as shown in Table 3. The variables were either in the form of natural logarithmic transformation of actual amounts or binary coded as presented in *Methods of data analysis*. The correlations between the variables are shown in Table 6.

Table 6

Regression analysis was conducted to identify the critical factors that influenced microcredit for household income and consumption smoothing. The results are shown in Table 7. As can be seen in Table 7, repayment period ($P < 0.001$), instalment amount ($P < 0.001$), and income ($P < 0.001$) were significantly related to the amount of borrowing for income and consumption smoothing. Interest rate was significant at 90 per cent significant level ($p < 0.10$). It was predicted in H1 that socio-demographic characteristics of low income people influence microcredit for income and consumption smoothing. However, H1 is not supported by the data. It was predicted in H2 that income and borrowing history of low income people influence microcredit for income and consumption smoothing. Here, borrowing history should be considered as a “must” variable since all respondents (100%) had unpaid prior borrowing. Income is also identified as a significant factor ($P < 0.001$). However, income source was not significant. Overall, we would like to interpret this result (2/3) as H2 is partially supported by the data. It was predicted in H3 that microcredit terms and conditions and distance to microfinance institution influence microcredit for income and consumption smoothing. We considered altogether five variables for H3, namely, repayment period, annual interest rate, instalment amount, upfront fee and distance to microfinance institution. The data supported for the significant influence from repayment period, interest rate and instalment amount. However, upfront fee and distance to microfinance institution were not significant. Therefore, we would like to interpret (3/5) this result as H3 is partially supported by the data.

Table 7

Conclusions and implications

Drawing from empirical data from economically disadvantaged communities living in Sri Lanka, we investigated microcredit delivered to low income communities with the ultimate intention of promoting micro-enterprises. The findings showed that communities use microcredit for income and consumption smoothing instead of income generating micro-entrepreneurial projects. This led us to conclude that the purpose for which microcredit is applied for could be different from the purposes for which it is meant for. In summary, the results showed that borrowers had taken

microcredit retroactively to repay loans previously undertaken by securing land title or self-employment as a guarantee and pawning, proactively for improvements in dwelling conditions such as roofing, walls and floor, and reactively to respond to crisis situations such as delay in rainfall and precautions for floods in farming. All the purposes for which microcredit is obtained in our study can be identified as risk-coping through income and consumption smoothing actions, instead of income generating actions. As stated in *Sample*, we have not pre-decided/planned the respondents to use their microcredit borrowing for smoothing actions. Still, 100% of our respondents, who held borrowings by the time of our data collection, had taken the credit for smoothing actions. This suggests that microcredit is popular for smoothing income and consumption. This is beyond the ideas and practice of microcredit as propagated by Yunus (2004). The experiences of low income people on the use of microcredit build a complex situation, which has implications for both theory and practice.

With regard to the contribution of the study to the literature, first, microcredit as a concept asserts that borrowing should be used for micro-enterprises and repaid via income generated from these enterprises. However, microfinance institutions provide microcredit to low income people for smoothing actions. From the part of low income borrowers, they usually do not have access to formal financial products due to their socio-economic background, incapability to produce security for credit, credit history and creditworthiness. As a result, on the one hand, low income people may perceive microcredit as an effective, flexible and low cost solution, which may decrease the need to sell household assets such as land, seeds and livestock, and as a mechanism to relax their dependence on exploitative relationship with private money-lenders. On the other hand, the delivery of microcredit without tight control from the side of microfinance institutions makes it highly appropriate for income and consumption smoothing. Hence, our findings shed light to the existing literature on the dual purpose (micro-enterprises vs smoothing) that microcredit plays in the economically disadvantaged communities. Similar situations had been observed by Bylander (2015), Busato et al. (2008), Chowdhury et al. (2005), Gerry et al. (2010), Ghalib et al. (2015) and Schroeder (2010) on the use of microcredit by low income communities in different country contexts. When microcredit is seen as a type of small instant loan, the findings of our study support the findings of previous studies that provided evidence for the use of small instant loans as a lifestyle facilitator (Autio et al., 2009; Erasmus & Mathunjwa, 2011; Patel et al., 2012; Wickramasinghe & Gurugamage, 2012). In current volatile

economic conditions, the demand for microcredit as well as other types of small instant loans for income and consumption smoothing could increase worldwide. We believe that we have provided valuable data and research insights for future researchers.

Second, the data showed that microfinance institutions charge high interest rates and hidden costs in comparison to other formal lending. The results showed that borrowers are subjected to registration fee, upfront fee, registration cancellation fee, late instalment fee in addition to interest fee. Since the credit was not utilized for income generating purposes, and as a result the findings suggest that borrowers expect to pay instalments and interest through their daily wage or self-employment. As a consequence, in practice, borrowers may struggle to repay loans heightening their vulnerabilities. From the part of microfinance institutions, they may have identified that lending money for low income people not only for income generating entrepreneurial activities but also for risk-coping is a profitable business. The findings presented in our study add value to the existing literature by providing an understanding of the behaviour of lenders with respect to the delivery of microcredit for risk-coping, as opposed to productive income generating purposes. Since we have not come across previous studies that resemble the scope of our study, we are not in a position to compare our findings with previous studies. As a consequence, the findings presented in our study add value to the existing literature by providing an understanding of lending behaviour that challenges the stated goals of microcredit.

Third, all the respondents had previous unpaid borrowing, and the majority had taken microcredit for the purpose of paying-off unpaid prior borrowing. This implies that borrowers unequivocally appreciate the convenience associated with microcredit for paying-off prior borrowing. This also implies that low income people may struggle in a vicious circle of being indebted. Previous studies also show that low income people using microcredit for paying-off prior borrowing, and repeat borrowers become poorer due to their inability to pay microcredit interest and installments (Bylander, 2015; Gerry & Li, 2010; Seefeldt, 2015). This suggests that microcredit had been used alongside borrowing taken from other formal and informal financial sources. When credit is interpreted as debt, the people living in economically disadvantaged communities are entangled in debt-related dependencies through self-help groups, which were created for the delivery of credit (or debt). Low income people may have to obtain further credit to pay-off current debt that was utilized for income and consumption smoothing. Overall, in the long-term the outcomes of risk-coping through microcredit would be costly to both borrowers

and society at large. Therefore, the findings of our study also imply the need for more future investigations on experiences of low income people and impact studies on the use of microcredit for purposes other than income generating micro-enterprises around the world.

Fourth, although the previous studies of Ghalib et al. (2015), Saeed et al. (2013), Murthy (2012) and Hussain (2003) identified the use of microcredit for income and consumption smoothing, these researchers had interpreted this borrowing for risk-coping as conditional cash transfers in the form of credit as a way of livelihood improvement of low income people. Such studies have not had regard to the negative effects of risk-coping through income and consumption smoothing as presented in the studies of Bylander (2015), Schroeder (2010) and Zeller (1999). The findings of our study also made it clear that, on the one hand, borrowers use microcredit for non-income generating purposes, and on the other hand, the borrowers may face the situation of paying-off microcredit through daily wage and non-remunerative work undertaken in self-employment, which could make them more vulnerable and poorer in the long-term. This situation could threaten the potential of microcredit as a development strategy targeting low income people. Therefore, the findings imply the need to specifically evaluate the issues surrounding the use and delivery of microcredit.

When microcredit is seen as a type of small instant loan, the studies of Melzer (2011) and Autio et al. (2009) also showed that low income people use small instant loans to repay prior borrowing or interest. Melzer (2011) showed that low income people were becoming poorer due to their inability to pay credit obtained as small instant loans. When evaluating the findings of previous studies, without solely focusing on low income communities, Bianchi and Levy (2013), Urahn (2012) and Autio et al. (2009) also showed that frequent borrowers of small instant loans used funds to balance-out a misaligned cash flow, and suggested that these borrowers could increasingly become repeat borrowers and may embark on a spiral of overspending. When comparing the socio-economic background of borrowers, results from our study as well as results from previous studies (Erasmus and Mathunjwa, 2011; Patel et al., 2012), it is possible to argue that borrowers' socio-economic background (low income, low level of education attainment) may influence ignorance in pertaining to the contractual obligations of credit agreements, and their subsequent vulnerability. If low income people are identified as a socially excluded group along with lone parents, people with disabilities and people with low education attainment, the findings of our study and Patel et al's (2012) suggest that socially excluded groups could become

increasingly vulnerable to debt problems. However, Patel et al. (2012) argued that vulnerability is not constant and it is influenced by broader economic and social factors, these are potential areas for future research.

Fifth, respondent characteristics of our study showed that the majority of microcredit borrowers were women. This situation has also been highlighted by several previous studies such as Unterhalter (2009), Ssendi and Anderson (2009), Edward and Olsen (2006) and Albee and Reid (1992). Our study also supports the contention for gender bias in microcredit requests as noted in the above mentioned previous studies. Further, our study supports the findings of Murthy (2012) and Chowdhury et al. (2005) that women have used microcredit for smoothing actions. Although the literature suggests the ability of microcredit to empower women, investigating such claims were beyond the scope of our study.

With regard to the contribution of the study for practice, first, it is evident that microfinance institutions have lent money and will continue to lend money for income and consumption smoothing unless there is restriction from the regulatory framework. The findings suggested the importance of repayment period, instalment amount and income in deciding the amount of credit requested for income and smoothing. Therefore, the findings could shed some light on the financial product development (such as loans) cycle in terms of factors that are critical for repayment.

Second, the findings suggest the need of some strategies to educate low income people on the areas of income, consumptions patterns, savings and borrowing. Without their active commitment, they will not be able to move away from demanding microcredit for income and consumption smoothing purposes.

Third, the findings imply the need for the implementation of policies to take low income people away from debt-related dependence in their communities. Considering the characteristics of low income groups – less assets and opportunities, low levels of education and engaged in job categories that are not recognized, regulated or protected by existing legal or regulatory frameworks - such policy responses would not be able to yield expected positive results in the short-term.

Fourth, given the use of microcredit for income and consumption smoothing and previous researchers' (e.g., Ghalib et al., 2015; Hussain, 2003; Murthy, 2012; Saeed et al., 2013) argument that low income people can increase household wellbeing through borrowing reduce

the credence of microcredit, and based on the findings of our study, we are reluctant to accept this argument. Therefore, the findings of our study would encourage practitioners to create a dialog between policy makers, researchers, civil society, microfinance institutions and the people living in economically disadvantaged communities to formulate firm strategies, which will enable low income people to escape from the debt trap. The conditions of poverty has implications for economic and social development of low income countries with millions of people living in poverty as well as middle income countries with poverty pockets around the world. Therefore, such a dialog would be beneficial for all.

Finally, there are some limitations in our research, which could provide insights on the areas for more research in the future. First, our findings can be generalized to low income communities with similar characteristics. Hence, future studies from other parts of the world may help to provide an enriched understanding of the topic. Second, we have not paid specific attention to the role of women in microcredit. When considering that more women are involved in obtaining microcredit, future investigations on thinking patterns of women in paying-off their prior debts with new debts (i.e., microcredit) would also be interesting. Third, the review of literature implied the risk involved in taking microcredit for income and consumption smoothing, which we have not explored in detail. The findings showed that borrowings were not used for the purpose of income generation, and therefore, taking on borrowing can be understood as taking on risk. Accordingly, further research could investigate the risk-taking patterns among low income people around the world for comparison purposes.

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Tables

Table 1. Sample description

<i>Age (in yrs):</i>		<i>Level of highest education (%):</i>	
Mean	40	Primary	55
Std. deviation	12	Secondary	45
Minimum	29		
Maximum	68		
<i>Number in the household:</i>		<i>Number of children completed primary education (%):</i>	
Mean	5	All of them completed	27
Std. deviation	2	Most of them completed	32
Minimum	4	Half of them completed	19
Maximum	9	All are in primary education	19
		Most of them not completed	3
<i>Number of dependents:</i>		<i>Community type (%):</i>	
Mean	3	Village	77
Std. deviation	2	Estate	23
Minimum	1		
Maximum	6		
<i>Gender (%):</i>		<i>Nature of residency in the area (%):</i>	
Female	96	Native	71
Male	4	Migrant	29

Table 2. Characteristic of being poor based on Progress out of Poverty Index* for Sri Lanka

	%		%
<i>Total members in the household:</i>		<i>Highest education level of the female head/spouse:</i>	
Six or more	23	Year 1 or less	9
Five	25	Years 2-7	30
Four	28	Years 8-9	14
Three	17	Year 10	26
One or two	7	No female head/spouse	0
		G.C.E. (O/L) or higher	21
<i>Number of members employed in government or semi-government entities:</i>		<i>Possession of an electric fan:</i>	
None	53	No	74
One or more	47	Yes	26
<i>Principal construction material of the floors:</i>		<i>Number of bedrooms:</i>	
Mud or other	26	None	9
Cement	68	1	28
Tile/Terrazzo	6	2	27
		3 or more	36
<i>Possession of a cooker (gas, kerosene, or electric):</i>		<i>Possession of a refrigerator:</i>	
No	91	No	79
Yes	9	Yes	21
<i>Possession of a bicycle; motorcycle etc; or motor car etc.†</i>		<i>Possession of a television and a VCD/DVD:</i>	
None	74	No television	23
Bicycle only	15	Television, but no VCD/DVD	26
Motorcycle etc (regardless of bicycle, but no motor car etc)	11	Television and VCD/DVD	51
Motor car etc (regardless of bicycle or motorcycle etc)	0		

* for more details on the specific poverty index for Sri Lanka and other countries visit Progress out of Poverty (2015)

† Possession of a bicycle; motorcycle, scooter, or three-wheeler; or motor car, van, bus, lorry, 2-wheel or 4-wheel tractor.

Table 3. Income, savings and prior borrowing

<i>Income source (%)</i> :	
Daily Wage	30
Self-employment/monthly pay	70
<i>Monthly Income (approximate, LKR)*</i> :	
Mean	22150
Std. deviation	7916
Minimum	4000
Maximum	38000
<i>Frequency of savings (%)</i> :	
Never	6
Occasionally	19
Monthly	75
<i>Possession of savings in a bank, post office, cooperative or microfinance institution (%)</i> :	
Yes	98
No	2
<i>Existence of unpaid borrowing[†] (%)</i> :	
Yes, from a financial institution or cooperative	96
Yes, informal money-lenders	4

* 1 US Dollar = 153 Sri Lankan Rupees (LKR)

[†] Includes credit obtained by securing land title or self-employment as a guarantee and pawning.

Table 4. Purpose for which microcredit loan actually utilized

	%
To pay-off prior borrowing	55
To improve dwelling characteristics such as roofing, walls and floor	23
To maintain self-employment due to delay in rainfall in farming, precautions for floods, and healthcare for wage earner of the household	15
To pay for sudden healthcare expenses of household members	4
To cover expenses of children's education	2
To pay for food and nutrition of household members	1

Table 5. Terms and conditions of borrowing for smoothing income and consumption

<i>Credit amount (LKR[*]):</i>	
Mean	57150
Std. deviation	29836
Minimum	6000
Maximum	100000
<i>Repayment period (Months):</i>	
Mean	19
Std. deviation	8
Minimum	3
Maximum	36
<i>Instalment amount (LKR[*]):</i>	
Mean	4614
Std. deviation	2387
Minimum	1120
Maximum	12500
<i>Interest and instalment payment (%):</i>	
Monthly	100
<i>Annual interest rate (%):</i>	
Mean	29
Std. deviation	1.74
Minimum	24
Maximum	32
<i>Requirement for upfront fee (%):</i>	
Yes (borrower make the payment)	100
<i>Upfront fee (LKR[*]):</i>	
Mean	600
Std. deviation	338
Minimum	50
Maximum	950
<i>Credit processing period (%):</i>	
Less than one month	100
<i>Security requirement for credit (%):</i>	
Yes - group security	100
<i>Sanctions for delays in instalment payment (%):</i>	
Yes - sanction to the borrower	100
<i>Sanctions on loan default (%):</i>	
Yes - sanction to the group	100
<i>Frequency of group meetings (%):</i>	
Twice a month	15
Once a month	85
<i>Distance to microfinance institution (KM):</i>	
Less than 10 KM	42
More than 10 KM	58

*1 US Dollar = 153 Sri Lankan Rupees (LKR)

Table 6. Correlations

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
1 Credit amount	1												
2 Repayment period	.652**	1											
3 Annual interest rate	.056	.185	1										
4 Installment amount	.714**	.237	.116	1									
5 Upfront fee	.130	.112	.172	.003	1								
6 Distance to microfinance institution	.216	.176	.234	.092	.189	1							
7 Age of the borrower	.137	.108	.272	.088	.127	.150	1						
8 Number in the household	.320*	.136	.239	.184	.094	.068	.045	1					
9 Number of dependents	.080	.055	.046	.218	.172	.235	.271	.634**	1				
10 Education of the borrower	.303*	.200	.149	.126	.221	.113	.247	.166	.044	1			
11 Community type	.178	.262	.290	.085	.254	.242	.086	.199	.167	.402**	1		
12 Nature of residency in the area	.211	.251	.231	.104	.246	.444**	.092	.064	.276	.504**	.155	1	
13 Monthly income	.513**	.275	.115	.399*	.389*	.107	.213	.333*	.009	.408**	.338*	.233	1
14 Income source	.121	.175	.142	.077	.580**	.197	.193	.095	.178	.351*	.430**	.403**	.442**

* p < 0.05; ** p < 0.01

Table 7. Summary of regression results

Variable	β (S.E.)	R ² (Adj.)	F
Repayment period	.616(.18) ***	.727 ***	8.793 ***
Annual interest rate	.216(.61)*		
Installment amount	.556(.21)***		
Upfront fee	.115(.37)		
Distance to microfinance institution	.187(.58)		
Age of the borrower	.139(.28)		
Number in the household	.138(.35)		
Number of dependents	.150(.25)		
Education of the borrower	.126(.19)		
Community type	.183(.26)		
Nature of residency in the area	.068(.27)		
Monthly income	.514(.36)***		
Income source	.151(.69)		

S.E.: Standard error; * p < 0.10; *** p < 0.001